

D6.2 Dissemination Plan

Project acronym:	FLOOD-serv
Project full title:	Public FLOOD Emergency and Awareness SERVICE
Grant agreement no.:	693599
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Document Reference:	D6.2 Dissemination Plan
Dissemination Level:	PUBLIC
Version:	Final
Date:	31/01/2018
License:	Creative Commons Attribution ShareAlike 4.0
Website:	<i>www.floodserv-project.eu</i>
Factsheet:	<i>http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/204804_en.html</i>
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History

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Modification reason</i>	<i>Modified by</i>
0.1	19.10.2016	Creation of the document structure and initial draft	Pantelis Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)
0.2	15.11.2016	Completed first draft and sent for internal review	Pantelis Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)
0.4	24.11.2016	Quality check	Adriana Prodan (SIVECO)
0.5	29.11.2016	Final reviewed deliverable	Pantelis Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)
Final	31.01.2018	Revision	Pantelis Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)

Table of contents

History.....	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	5
List of tables	6
List of abbreviations.....	7
Executive summary	9
1 Introduction	10
1.1 The FLOOD-serv Project	10
1.2 WP6 Stakeholders Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation	11
1.3 The deliverable: D6.2 Dissemination Plan	12
1.3.1 Scope and objectives the deliverable	12
1.3.2 Intended audience of the deliverable	12
1.3.3 Structure of the deliverable	13
1.4 Relation of D6.2 to other WP6 deliverables.....	13
1.5 Quality Management.....	14
2 Communication	15
2.1 Objectives of Communication Activities.....	15
2.2 Phases of Communication Activities	16
2.3 Target Audience of the Communication Activities.....	16
2.3.1 End-users	17
2.3.2 Decision Makers/Replication Actors	19
2.3.3 Stakeholders	20
2.3.4 Policy Makers.....	21
2.3.5 Funding Authority – European Commission.....	22
2.3.6 General Public from EU countries	22
3 Dissemination Plan	23
3.1 Dissemination Objectives	23
3.2 About the Dissemination Strategy	23
3.3 Dissemination methods, tools and channels.....	25
3.3.1 Dissemination methods.....	25
3.3.2 Dissemination tools	25
3.3.3 Dissemination channels.....	26
3.3.3.1 FLOOD-serv website	26

3.3.3.2	Academic Journals	27
3.3.3.3	Non-scientific publications	27
3.3.3.4	Public Events.....	27
3.3.3.5	Relevant Websites	28
3.3.3.6	FLOOD-serv social media accounts.....	28
3.3.3.7	Mailing Lists	29
3.3.3.8	Other Channels.....	30
4	Calendar of Dissemination Activities	31
4.1	The Calendar.....	31
4.2	WP6 actions performed until M4.....	38
5	Performance Measurement of Dissemination Activities	39
5.1	Quantitative Measurements	39
5.1.1	Website’s indicators measurement.....	39
5.1.2	Facebook’s indicators measurement	39
5.1.3	Twitter’s indicators measurement	40
5.1.4	LinkedIn’s indicators measurement	40
5.1.5	Google+ indicators measurement	40
5.1.6	Newsletter’s indicators measurement	40
5.1.7	Digital Publishing Platforms indicators measurement	41
5.1.8	YouTube’s indicators measurement.....	41
5.1.9	Media indicators measurement	41
5.1.10	Other indicators measurement	42
5.2	Qualitative Measurements.....	43
6	Conclusions	44
	APPENDIX I – WP6 contact points	45
	APPENDIX II – Dissemination Rules and Guidelines	46
	APPENDIX III – Reporting Template	52
	APPENDIX IV – Targeted scientific journals	56
	APPENDIX V – Targeted Events	58
	APPENDIX VI – Related EU funded projects	59
	APPENDIX VII – WP6 performed actions until M4.....	61

List of figures

<i>Figure 1 : Communication in EU funded projects and its subsets</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Figure 2 : Phases of Communication Activities.....</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>Figure 3 : Target Audience.....</i>	<i>17</i>
<i>Figure 4 : Project logo</i>	<i>61</i>
<i>Figure 5 : Project’s website.....</i>	<i>61</i>
<i>Figure 6 : Facebook Page.....</i>	<i>61</i>
<i>Figure 7 : Google+ Profile</i>	<i>62</i>
<i>Figure 8 : Twitter Account</i>	<i>62</i>
<i>Figure 9 : LinkedIn Account.....</i>	<i>62</i>
<i>Figure 10 : Scribd Account</i>	<i>63</i>
<i>Figure 11 : Slideshare Account</i>	<i>63</i>
<i>Figure 12 : Issuu Account.....</i>	<i>63</i>

List of tables

Table 1 : Intended audience of the deliverable	13
Table 2 : Relation of D6.2 to other WP6 deliverables	14
Table 3 : End users	19
Table 4 : Stakeholders	21
Table 5 : Rationale of the FLOOD-serv Dissemination Plan.....	25
Table 6 : Calendar of FLOOD-serv main dissemination Activities	37
Table 7 : Website’s indicators measurement	39
Table 8 : Facebook’s indicators measurement	39
Table 9 : Twitter’s indicators measurement.....	40
Table 10 : LinkedIn indicators measurement	40
Table 11 : Google+indicators measurement	40
Table 12 : Newsletter’s indicators measurement	41
Table 13 : Digital Publishing Platforms indicators measurement.....	41
Table 14 : You tube’s indicators measurement	41
Table 15 : Media indicators measurement	42
Table 16 : Other indicators measurement	42
Table 17 : List of targeted events	58
Table 18 : List of related EU funded projects.....	60

List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
ANO	A.N.O. SISTEMAS DE INFORMATICA E SERVICOS LDA
ANSWARETECH	ANSWARETECH SL
BILBAO	AYUNTAMIENTO DE BILBAO
BSK	BRATISLAVSKY SAMOSPRAVNY KRAJ
CELLENT	CELLENT AG
CMVNF	MUNICIPIO DE VILA NOVA DE FAMALICAO
D6.2	D6.2 Dissemination Plan
D6.3	D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan
D6.4	D6.4 Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan
D6.5	D6.5 Sustainability and Exploitation Final Plan
D6.6	D6.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report
DDNI	INTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE - DEZVOLTARE DELTA DUNARI
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EXDWARF	EXDWARF CONSULTING SRO
GA	Grant Agreement
GENOVA	COMUNE DI GENOVA
GIS	Geographic Information System
GOV2U	GOVERNMENT TO YOU
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IP TULCEA	INSTITUTIA PREFECTULUI JUDETUL TULCEA
REA	Research Executive Agency
SIVECO	SIVECO S.A. ROMANIA
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The current document under the title "*D6.2 Dissemination plan*" describes the dissemination strategy and the respective actions that will be implemented by the FLOOD-serv consortium during the project's lifetime. Moreover, it defines partners' roles and responsibilities and sets the success criteria for the evaluation of the dissemination activities foreseen in the presented plan. This plan aims to achieve significant awareness of the initiative, an understanding of its benefits and active interaction with necessary stakeholders.

D6.2 is a public deliverable of this project, part of WP6. It also consists information about the project's scope and objectives as well as the description of WP6 in order to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the DoW and the other WP6 deliverables is requested from the reader. Overall, it is based on, and is consistent with the DoW and the GA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

1 Introduction

The current chapter gives information about the project's scope and objectives as well as the description of WP6 in order to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the DoW and the other WP6 deliverables is requested from the reader. A brief outline of this document is also provided.

1.1 The FLOOD-serv Project

FLOOD-serv is a three year project that was launched in August 2016 aiming to raise awareness on flood risks and enable collective risk mitigation solutions and response actions by using the collaborative power of ICT networks and citizens' involvement. It is an Innovation Action funded under the "ICT-enabled open government" topic (*INSO-1-2015*) of the Horizon 2020 programme - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Europe in a changing world - Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies.

The overall objective of FLOOD-serv is to develop and to provide a pro-active and personalised citizen-centric public service application that will enhance the involvement of the citizen and will harness the collaborative power of ICT networks (*networks of people, of knowledge, of sensors*) to raise awareness on flood risks and to enable collective risk mitigation solutions and response actions.

The general objectives of the project are:

- Empowering local communities to directly participate in the design of emergency services dealing with floods mitigation actions.
- Harness the power of new technologies, such as social media, and mobile technologies to increase the efficiency of public administrations in raising public awareness and education regarding floods risks, effects and impact.
- Encourage the development and implementation of long-term, cost-effective and environmentally sound mitigation actions related to floods through an ICT-enabled cooperation and collaboration of all stakeholders: government, private sector, NGOs and other civil society organizations as well as citizens.

The specific objectives are:

- Utilize best available data to identify the location and potential impacts of natural hazards on people, property and natural environment.
- Improve systems that provide warning and emergency communications.
- Provide support for the public authorities and government institutions' hazard mitigation efforts, including planning and action coordination.
- Inform the public on the risk exposure to natural hazards and ways to increase the public's capability to prepare, respond, recover and mitigate the impacts of these events.

The project aims at having a strong impact on the efficiency and overall adoption of new pro-active and personalised citizen-centric public service applications based on new web technologies and mobile technologies. **Technically the project will focus on developing a collaborative platform** that will link citizen, public authorities and other stakeholders and enables the public to be warned en masse so that actions can be taken to reduce the adverse effects of the flood. The proposed solution will manage big data acquired from various external data sources (*sensors, social media, open data, etc.*), large volumes of publicly available data. The project will prepare, develop and implement test pilots, which will test, verify, demonstrate and validate the project solutions in different conditions and different

areas of Europe. Such scalable experiments and prototypes are set to be organized in 5 pilot sites:

- **Danube Delta**, Romania
- **Genova**, Italy
- **Bilbao**, Spain
- **Bratislava Self-Governing Region**, Slovakia
- **Ave Valley Region**, Portugal

The project will implement a bottom-up approach in different catchment areas across Europe. FLOOD-serv will deploy and pilot a user-driven participatory solution where public value is created by the ability to share, interact and collaborate between actors and by harnessing human and ICT capabilities and open data. It is expected that the project will identify and involve relevant stakeholders who can act as users that will make the adoption of FLOOD-serv methods and tools more likely.

Potential users and customers (*citizens, public authorities, researchers, companies, public institutions, NGO's etc.*) will be empowered by the project to share their ideas, knowledge, skills, and experiences in order to explore new methods and tools that can enhance their own disaster resilience and that of their communities.

FLOOD-serv is carried out by a multi-disciplinary, complementary consortium consisting of 12 partners representing companies (*large industries and SMEs*), public authorities, research institutes, and NGOs from 7 different EU member states: Austria, Belgium, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Spain. The members of the consortium are:

- **SIVCO ROMANIA SA**, Romania (*Coordinator*)
- **CELLENT AG**, Austria
- **ANSWARETECH SL**, Spain
- **GOVERNMENT TO YOU**, Belgium
- **COMUNE DI GENOVA**, Italy
- **INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE DELTA DUNARII**, Romania
- **AYUNTAMIENTO DE BILBAO**, Spain
- **ANO, SISTEMAS DE INFORMÁTICA E SERVIÇOS, LDA**, Portugal
- **EXDWARF CONSULTING S.R.O.**, Slovakia
- **INSTITUTIA PREFECTULUI- JUDETUL TULCEA**, Romania
- **BRATISLAVA SELF-GOVERNING REGION**, Slovakia
- **MUNICÍPIO DE VILA NOVA DE FAMALICÃO**, Portugal

1.2 WP6 Stakeholders Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation

The work package with title “Stakeholders Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation” (*WP6*) is a subset of the FLOOD-serv project.

According to the Description of Work (*DoW*), WP6 is assigned to:

- Launch an effective internal and external communication and dissemination strategy while assisting other work packages to meet their outreach objectives.
- Establish a consistent and distinctive project identity and maintain a favorable reputation.
- Communicate and disseminate - widely and effective - the project's objective's, methodology, benefits and findings among wide variety of stakeholders, from public bodies who are involved in flood mitigation and response to policy-makers and academics, as well as the general public in order to maximize the project's impact and

visibility and to ensure the take-up of the pilot methodologies and tools in the long-term.

- Reach and involve target groups through systematic use of a variety of dissemination techniques and means
- Link with other projects and CSAs funded under the ICT-enabled open government call as well as other international projects and organizations of relevance for the FLOOD-serv project, integrating knowledge coming from these projects, investigating collaboration opportunities and exploiting synergies.
- Define a post-project sustainability and exploitation strategy and planning to sustain project outcomes and maximize its impact.

For achieving these objectives, WP6 will use a series of online and offline tools and strategies during the whole duration of the project with the aim of bringing attention to the project, gaining trust and ensuring acceptance of the results. All partners have an active role in this work package, participate and undertake activities linked to specific tasks of it.

1.3 The deliverable: D6.2 Dissemination Plan

1.3.1 Scope and objectives the deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to describe the dissemination strategy and the actions that will implemented by the FLOOD-serv consortium during the project’s lifetime. In addition, to define partners’ roles and responsibilities and set the success criteria of the aforementioned actions. The expected result of the Dissemination Plan is to achieve significant awareness of the initiative, an understanding of its benefits and active interaction with necessary stakeholders.

The dissemination plan presented in this document will be regularly reviewed and updated based on project’s evolution and new knowledge acquired. If needed, corrective actions will be taken, in close collaboration with the project consortium.

1.3.2 Intended audience of the deliverable

<i>Intended audience</i>	<i>Reasons for interest in reading</i>
FLOOD-serv project partners	To be informed about the project’s dissemination plan and the timeline of performing the scheduled actions.
European Commission	To assess the quality of the document and the presented planned actions.
Target groups <i>End-users, decision makers/replication actors, stakeholders, policy makers</i>	To be informed about the project in general, its scope, the dissemination activities that will be performed during its implementation and discover how they could be benefited.
Representatives of organizations involved into similar projects	To share knowledge, information, best practices and so on that could be useful in implementing their respective activities. Also this document can introduce them the FLOOD-serv project and potential synergies in the

	field of dissemination could be identified.
Anyone interested	To be informed about the available tools and methods for promoting in general ideas and/or results of a project. Moreover, to raise awareness on project's topic.

Table 1 : Intended audience of the deliverable

1.3.3 Structure of the deliverable

This document is comprised of 6 chapters and 7 appendices. The first chapter introduces the reader to the FLOOD-serv project, its objectives as well as the objectives of WP6. Additionally, it describes the scope of the current deliverable, the audience that is addressed to and its relation to other WP6 deliverables.

The second chapter shows how communication process in EU funded project is interrelated to dissemination. The third chapter presents in detail the dissemination strategy and elaborates all its aspects, where the fourth chapter forms a representation of the scheduled FLOOD-serv dissemination activities on a calendar.

The fifth chapter sets the success criteria for the evaluation of the dissemination activities foreseen in the presented plan. Lastly, the sixth chapter consists the conclusion of this document.

1.4 Relation of D6.2 to other WP6 deliverables

This deliverable is interrelated with other deliverables of WP6. The following list presents the dependencies and relation:

<i>WP6 Deliverables</i>	<i>Dependencies and relation</i>
<i>D6.1 Community of Interest Build-up & Engagement Strategy</i>	It has been released on Month 3 (<i>October 2016</i>). The deliverable presents the typologies of stakeholders and end users for FLOOD-serv Platform and their potential motivation to participate in the project and a detailed plan for creating a wider constituency within which the consortium will operate and produce its work, including targeted actions to ensure the active management of the members of the Community of Interest. Participation in the Community of Interest will be heavily promoted through the communication and dissemination activities of the project in the pilot sites, which are presented in the D6.2.
<i>D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 19 (<i>February 2018</i>). This deliverable will update the D6.2. It will report the communication and dissemination activities implemented during the first 18 months of the project and will present the dissemination plan for the next 18 months of the project.
<i>D6.4 Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 20 (<i>March 2018</i>). The strategy for exploitation of project results and for ensuring their sustainability after the end of the project depends on

	effective dissemination strategy, which is presented in the D6.2.
<i>D6.5 Sustainability and Exploitation Final Plan</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 35 (<i>June 2019</i>). This deliverable updates the D6.4 and it is also related to D6.2, since successful exploitation and sustainability depends on effective dissemination strategy
<i>D6.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 36 (<i>July 2019</i>). This deliverable will report the activities that will be implemented during the whole project duration, based on the strategy and action plan presented in D6.1 and updated in D6.3

Table 2 : Relation of D6.2 to other WP6 deliverables

1.5 Quality Management

Quality management assures the quality of the project deliverables and the quality of the processes used to manage and create the deliverables. Thus, the initial ideas were presented during the FLOOD-serv kick off meeting and the consortium discussed them thoroughly providing valuable feedback. Moreover, regular teleconferences followed and more ideas were elaborated.

WP6 leader, Gov2u, prepared the first draft of the current document and distributed to WP6 partners for reviewing and contribution. This deliverable uses the correct template that the consortium has designated and language quality control has been performed.

2 Communication

The term of **Communication**¹, in EU funded projects, means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

The scope of this document is to present to the reader the dissemination plan of the FLOOD-serv consortium in order to promote its results to the target audiences. However, dissemination consists a subset of communication and within this framework, the current chapter is dedicated to communication for ensuring that all types of readers will be able to comprehend the information contained herein without having prior knowledge on the topic.

Figure 1 : Communication in EU funded projects and its subsets

2.1 Objectives of Communication Activities

The objectives of the communication activities of the project throughout its lifetime are:

- To widely and effectively communicate the project's objectives, methodology, benefits and findings among wide variety of stakeholders, from public bodies who are involved in flood mitigation and response to policy-makers and academics, as well as the general public in order to maximize the project's impact and visibility and to ensure the take-up of the pilot methodologies and tools in the long-term.
- To show how the aims and outcomes of FLOOD-serv are relevant to flood risk management and to people's everyday lives.
- To establish a dialog with those who can contribute to development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of the project results.
- To link with other projects funded under the ICT-enabled open government call as well as other international projects and organizations of relevance for the FLOOD-serv project, integrating knowledge coming from these projects, investigating collaboration opportunities and exploiting synergies.

¹ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

- To raise the profile of the organisations carrying out the project at local, national and international level and highlight the European added value of activities supported by Horizon 2020 programme.
- To raise public awareness that the EU money are well spent.

2.2 Phases of Communication Activities

The communication activities of the project during its lifecycle could be divided into the following three phases:

- **First Phase - Communication for Awareness** (*August 2016 - January 2017*): It is focused on general promotion of the project, ensuring that the project is appropriately recognized on a wide scale and securing interest and engagement of key stakeholders. It entails developing the project website and initial communication materials, developing the project's internet presence on social networks and regular dissemination of the project developments (*via available communication tools*).
- **Second Phase - Communication for Action** (*February 2017 - March 2018*): It involves the promotion of the interim results to the target audience, further engagement with key stakeholders to motivate their participation; continue establishing contacts and relations with new stakeholders; initiate knowledge sharing among related projects.
- **Final Phase – Communication of Final Results** (*April 2018 - July 2019*): It involves the promotion of the final results, motivate further participation of stakeholders in the project events, promote exchange of experiences and knowledge sharing with related initiatives and take-up of the project results.

Figure 2 : Phases of Communication Activities

2.3 Target Audience of the Communication Activities

The target audience of the FLOOD-serv communication activities can be divided into six main categories:

1. **End-users** - Are the ones that direct benefit from the project results;
2. **Decision makers/replication actors** - Are those that have the decision power for the adoption of the project results in the countries where pilot cities will be implemented;
3. **Stakeholders** - Are the ones that have a direct or indirect benefit from the project;
4. **Policy makers** - Are those that can integrate project results into policies;
5. **Funding Authority** - Research Executive Agency (*REA*)/European Commission;
6. **General Public** from EU countries.

Figure 3 : Target Audience

For each category of target audience, a detailed analysis of its typology and the reason why the group is targeted is presented in the following sub-chapters.

2.3.1 End-users

S/N	Group	Description
i	End-users of the flood risk management proactive and personalized citizen-centric public service application	<p>Individuals and institutions/organizations from the pilot sites (<i>Danube Delta - Romania, Genova- Italy, Bilbao - Spain, Bratislava Self-Governing Region - Slovakia, Ave Valley Region - Portugal</i>).</p> <p>The project plans to establish a Community of Interest consisting of existing communities of people from the pilot sites and engage with them to shape the direction in which the FLOOD-serv platform will be developed, tested and evaluated.</p> <p>They will be empowered by the project to share their ideas, knowledge, skills, and experiences in order to explore new methods and tools that can enhance their own disaster resilience and that of their communities.</p> <p>The Community of Interest will allow the Consortium to identify real, actual needs in the potential user pool and take them into consideration; to adapt the platforms to meeting these needs and to respond to feedback.</p> <p>The project will provide opportunities for community members to take leadership roles and this can motivate many members of the community to get involved in the process of flood risk mitigation and response.</p> <p>The following persons and institutions/organizations from the pilot sites will be targeted:</p>

		<p>a. Grassroots groups and organizations interested in the management and conservation actions regarding water and land</p> <p>b. Land owners and administrators of properties</p> <p>c. Members of NGOs that are service providers (<i>e.g. shelter</i>) and volunteers' organisations of civil protection</p> <p>d. Informal citizens networks (<i>offline and online</i>) that are engaged in social issues</p> <p>e. Trade organizations which are representatives of interest groups (<i>e.g. forestry and agriculture, tourism, hunting, fishery, etc.</i>)</p> <p>f. Persons that experienced a flood in the past or were affected with material losses due to a flood in the pilot sites</p> <p>g. University students who are tech-savvy and engaged in social issues</p> <p>h. School teachers</p> <p>i. Water users associations</p> <p>j. Emergency planners and services</p> <p>k. River basin authorities</p> <p>l. Public authorities dealing with emergency services</p> <p>m. Individuals with expertise in physical science and engineering, geographical science, social and behavioral science, economics, and public health with professional experience from research, public policy, emergency and disaster management</p> <p>n. Computer programmers and others involved in software development (<i>technology enthusiasts, early adopters, geeks, IT professionals from companies, SMEs and ICT start-ups</i>)</p> <p>o. The wider general public, i.e. communities/neighborhoods including the resident population as well as local businesses (<i>companies from the sectors concerned with water supply and purification, dredging, maritime activities, fishing activities, expert ecological consulting services, waste water treatment, irrigation, hydro power, mining, agriculture, tourism promotion, leisure activities, transport, architecture and construction etc.</i>) who could be affected by the flood risk management issues and impacted by measures.</p>
ii.	Research community	Digital social innovation organisation and networks, researchers in areas such as flood risk management, participatory open government, open data integration,

		<p>human sensing, content harvesting, distributed knowledge co-creation, decision support systems, collective intelligence, data mining etc. as well as international organisations involved in flooding issues (<i>e.g. IAHR- The International Association of Hydraulic Engineering and Research, IAHS-the International Association of Hydrological Sciences, EGS- the European Geophysical Society etc.</i>).</p> <p>They could be interested to feed the project results and know-how into further RTD projects related to ICT-enabled government, collective intelligence, PSI re-use, open data, etc.</p>
iii.	Academic Community	<p>European schools and training institutes focused on teaching and training on a variety of topics related to flood management, social science and technology, public affairs & administration.</p> <p>The know-how acquired in the context of the project could be exploited by the academic community for educational purposes with the main aim of defining and offering to students innovative topics for theses and projects, new courses contents, developing products such as books or manuals from research and lessons learned during the project.</p>
iv.	Business and industry	<p>including both ICT solution providers and consulting industry with interest in Public sector innovation</p> <p>They can develop commercial ICT applications based on research and technological innovations created by the project and consult governments and other public service organizations on how to harness the technology developed by the project to transform their businesses.</p>

Table 3 : End users

2.3.2 Decision Makers/Replication Actors

Decision makers and practitioners of national civil protection authorities across Europe, National/Regional Hydrological Services, emergency planners and services, civil protection experts, municipal departments/government agencies in charge of water and sewage, electricity provision, broadband provision, municipal heating, spatial planning and construction, transportation, environment and health, IT/GIS.

They may be interested in the project results from the application side (*customers*) for adoption and/or extending this system to other policy areas related to sustainability (*e.g. management of other types of disasters, community policing, early warning etc.*), to different sites in the pilot countries and to different countries, at the same level as the pilot system and at lower and higher scales.

2.3.3 Stakeholders

S/N	Group	Description
i.	EU level, national and local non-governmental Organisations (NGOs)	<p>representatives of public bodies (<i>EUPAN – The European Public Administration Network</i>), of European Regions (AER - the Assembly of European Regions, EU-level and national NGOs and their networks active in the disaster reduction and emergency management field, open government data advocates and access to information advocates (e.g. <i>Open Knowledge Foundation, Access Info Europe, EDRI-European Digital Rights, Communia- the international association on the digital public domain etc.</i>).</p> <p>They can use the results of the project for advocacy activities aimed at institutional reforms at local level related to crisis management and emergency response process (e.g. adoption by the governments of platforms for collective awareness that can be used for feeding data contributed by distributed human and environmental sources for improved early warning system and for more participatory democratic processes for problem solving) They can also use the results of the project for influencing policies at national and EU level aimed at stimulating the creation and delivery of new public services utilising new web technologies, coupled with open public data. Some of them may have connections and collaborations with the local groups of interest for this project, thus helping us to reach them or to disseminate the project results among them.</p>
ii.	Multi-stakeholder group of partners across various disciplines for innovation	<p>(e.g. <i>research, industry, finance, NGO, ICT, etc.</i>), as well as the demand and supply sides of innovation- The Steering Group, Task Force and Action Groups under the European Innovation Partnership on Water, European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities, European projects in the area of digital social innovation, other projects funded under the INSO-1-2014/2015 (ICT-enabled open government) topic - <i>CLARITY, DIGIWHIST, Euth, Mobile-Age, OpenBudgets.eu, OpenGovIntelligence, RECAP, ROUTE-TO-PA, SIMPATICO, smarticipate, smarticipate, STEP, WeGovNow, WeLive and YourDataStories</i> - as well as other international projects and organizations of relevance for the FLOOD-serv project.</p> <p>They can integrate knowledge coming from our project. The FLOOD-serv Consortium can investigate collaboration opportunities and exploiting synergies with these groups and projects.</p>
iii.	Science advisory bodies	Horizon 2020 expert advisory group on Societal Challenge 6, Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative and

	/ Expert groups	<p>reflective societies, the High Level Group of Scientific Advisors of the EC Scientific Advice Mechanism, The EU’s Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group etc..</p> <p>The project findings may be of interest for them when provide opinions, reports and recommendations for action at EU and at national level to foster the ICT-enabled public sector innovation</p>
iv.	DRM Knowledge Centre	<p>Within the European Flood Awareness System it provides a Forum of Information Exchange to have a harmonized approach to Disaster Monitoring.</p> <p>The results of FLOOD-serv are related to flood disasters monitoring, therefore are of interest to the DRM Knowledge Centre.</p>
v.	European and international Standardization bodies	<p><i>(E.g. ISO, CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Coordination Group ‘Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities’ SSCC-CG, OGC-Open Geodata Consortium etc.)</i></p> <p>Standardization bodies have enormous influence within the European Union as they produce and recommend technical and legal standards to address the needs of affected adopters of new technologies.</p> <p>BS 11200:2014 Crisis management, and ISO 22320:2011 Societal security – Emergency management – Requirements for incident response are two standards offer guidance and good practice to help organisations plan, establish, operate, maintain and improve their crisis management capability. Compliance with these standards is crucial for ensuring interoperability and for this reason they will be followed by the partners in issuing the project requirements as much as possible. FLOOD-serv may contribute to the standardization process if specific extensions and refinements are required, by making recommendations in this regard to the standardization bodies.</p>
vi.	Media from pilot sites as well as national, European and international media.	<p>Media institutions are not only stakeholders in the project but also the means to raise awareness about the project. Therefore media serve both as a goal and as a means.</p>

Table 4 : Stakeholders

2.3.4 Policy Makers

Policy makers in both legislative and executive bodies at local, national, regional and EU level (*MEPs, MPs, ministers, mayors*) from across Europe that holds the responsibility for the coordination and implementation of eGovernment services and for disaster risk management. They can use the project knowledge and results to drive better policies by embedding the results into policies and practices at local, regional, national and EU levels related to flood

event management policy domain (*e.g. stimulating public participation and collective actions*) and to ICT enabled open government.

2.3.5 Funding Authority – European Commission

The FLOOD-serv Consortium has an informative dialogue with the Project Officer representing the Commission. The Project officer will be informed about interesting topics, news and events concerning the project. EC could also support the dissemination of the project. In this regard, news and success stories related to the project can be submitted for publications and websites managed by the European Commission.

2.3.6 General Public from EU countries

The EU citizens will be informed about the European added value of activities supported by Horizon 2020 programme and how the aims and outcomes of FLOOD-serv are relevant to the people's own disaster resilience and that of their communities.

3 Dissemination Plan

The term “Dissemination²” in all EU funded projects means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. According to the Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation and work programme 2014-2015, a **plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results³** is necessary and the obligation to submit such plan arises at the project proposal stage.

In our project’s case, following the actions foreseen in the DoW, this document presents only the FLOOD-serv Dissemination Plan while in M20 (*March 2018*) the initial exploitation plan will be formed and submitted within the deliverable under the title “**D6.4 Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan**”.

3.1 Dissemination Objectives

Dissemination consists a subset of project’s communication activities and it has the following objectives:

- To spread the word about the project results and lessons learnt as far as possible in order to enable others to benefit from the activities and experiences of this project and to maximize the impact of research;
- To achieve a return of investment by reaching out to as many potential users of the project results;
- To transfer the research-based knowledge to the ones that can best make use of it
- To generate market demand for the products or services developed;
- To promote the developments of the project to potential end users aiming to attract their attention about the FLOOD-serv solution;
- To prepare the ground for the sustainability and further exploitation of the results beyond the project lifetime.

3.2 About the Dissemination Strategy

The purpose of the Dissemination Strategy described in the current section is to provide an overall framework and guidelines for the successful implementation of all dissemination activities and ensuring that are aligned with the overall goals of the project. To that end the strategy is composed of interrelated activities whose purpose is to inform the target groups and the end-users about the produced results of the project with the scope of getting them involved and possibly contribute by providing feedback to consortium.

Dissemination strategy concerns and has an impact on all the work packages of the project, which is why FLOOD-serv partners should align their work e.g. drafting their deliverables, conducting pilots, attending conferences, etc. accordingly with this strategy. The involvement of all partners is also needed in order to successfully present their findings and create in general a positive reputation around the project that will lead also in successful exploitation actions.

The rationale behind a successful Dissemination Strategy is imprinted by answering the following questions:

² Source: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

³ Source: https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/FS-Plan-for-the-exploitation-and-dissemination-of-results_1.pdf

- **Why?** (*Reasons for dissemination*)
- **What?** (*Information to be disseminated*)
- **How ?**(*Tools and Channels*)
- **Who?** (*Consortium partner/s*)
- **When?** (*Time*)
- **To Whom?** (*Categories of Audience*)
- **Where?** (*Location*)

Following up the above questions, the FLOOD-serv Dissemination Plan is based and compliant within the presented concept.

Questions	Description
Why? <i>(Reasons for dissemination)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contractual obligation of the consortium - attract potential end-users - receive feedback from the end users - prepare the ground for the exploitation actions
What? <i>(information to be disseminated)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project achievements: Anything that has been achieved and how it was achieved. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Examples:</u> <i>completion of project events, deliverables, tasks, work packages, milestones</i> - Project results: New knowledge items, new products that FLOOD-serv will deliver. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Examples:</u> <i>public deliverables, good practice and methodologies applied for implementing and delivering the project results</i> - Lessons learnt (<i>bad or good ones</i>): Anything related to the project that is useful for third parties to become aware and either endorse or avoid.
How? <i>(Tools and Channels)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Via the project website - Via the project e-newsletters - Via social media accounts - Via publications - peer-reviewed journal articles - Via press releases - Via third party events, conferences, workshops, fairs and exhibitions - Via articles in non-scientific magazines
Who? <i>(Consortium partner/s)</i>	The project partner that leads the activity as well as the contributors
To Whom?	- Stakeholders

<i>(categories of audience)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End-users - Decision makers/replication actors - Policy makers
When <i>(Time)</i>	The scheduled time within the project's lifecycle that the activity will occur.
Where? <i>(Location)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local level in pilot sites - National level in the project partner countries - European level

Table 5 : Rationale of the FLOOD-serv Dissemination Plan

The Dissemination Plan of the project is fully presented in **chapter 4** under the form of a “calendar” for ensuring that all types of audience, without excluding anyone interested around the FLOOD-serv project, will be able to have access to the information contained herein.

3.3 Dissemination methods, tools and channels

3.3.1 Dissemination methods

Dissemination will be conducted via **publications** (*scientific dissemination*), **face-to-face activities** (*workshops, meetings, focus group, interviews, project events co-located to major conferences*), **Internet-based activities** (*project website, Web 2.0 services, groups, websites, e-newsletters, direct distribution via e-mail, online discussion lists, online collaboration space*), **press-based activities** (*press releases, TV/radio interviews, articles*), **paper-based direct distribution** (*brochures, flyers*).

Effective networking is about building strong and useful relationships over time that can lead to mutual understanding and trust and which can help the raising of project's positive reputation and take-up of its results in the long term. A mapping of similar or complementary initiatives and cooperation frameworks as well as of potential multipliers will be undertaken at the start of the project.

The aim is to **establish collaborations** with such initiatives, networks and organizations to foster awareness at an EU-level, to share experiences and to widen the project approach. These collaborations will produce an effect greater than the sum of their individual effects (*synergies*). In this regard, activities such as reciprocal links with the project websites/institutional websites, posts on social media accounts as well co-organization of joint dissemination events could be realized. The initial list of initiatives that will be approached for these purposes is presented in the **Appendix VI**.

3.3.2 Dissemination tools

A variety of tools will be used in order to promote the results of the project and assist WP6 in the dissemination activities. These tools are presented in the list below:

- **Press releases** for announcing to target audience as well as to general public in pilot sites and beyond across EU countries the important achievements. These press releases will be published in English and depending on the media targeted, the press releases will be also published in partners' languages from pilot sites.

- **E-Newsletters issues** will be published throughout the project's lifetime. The e-Newsletters will convey the FLOOD-serv developments as well as events and conferences where the project will be presented. Its content will be in English.
- **Roll-up banners** will be created for enhancing partners' dissemination activities in events / conferences / workshops etc.
- **Videos tutorials and/or demos** related to project's developments.
- **Final project brochure** in printed and digital format to highlight the final results of the project and point out in a clear message the value proposition and benefits of the FLOOD-serv platform. Moreover, this brochure will be distributed to the participants of project's final event in Brussels.
- **Project presentation and results in PPT format** that will briefly describes the FLOOD-serv findings and will complementary assist the members of the consortium in presenting the project in pitch events, brokerage events, workshops, conferences and so on.

The results that will be promoted through the aforementioned tools will mainly be under the form of:

- Peer-reviewed journal articles;
- Poster and oral presentations at academic conferences;
- A research brief presenting a summary information on research activities' results of the project will be created in order to be disseminated among EU research community (*via direct email to collaborators/research projects, via project website and via third party events and final conference of the project*);
- Articles submitted to non-scientific publications;
- Public deliverables of the project.

As far as the FLOOD-serv platform is concerned access during the lifetime of the project will be free of charge. Outside the project duration the access to FLOOD-serv platform will be based on the agreements between partners taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights (*IPR*). The deliverable D6.4 "*Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan*" will detail all of this aspects within FLOOD-serv project.

3.3.3 Dissemination channels

Multiple channels are considered in order to have an effective dissemination of the project's results. The main dissemination channels will be the FLOOD-serv website, its social media accounts, public events organized by the project for knowledge transfer, third party conferences and workshops, magazines and research journals.

3.3.3.1 FLOOD-serv website

The project's website will be a versatile and resourceful dissemination tool, also serving the sustainability purposes since it aims to sustain the projects results after the end of the project. As project nears the end of its execution the emphasis of the project website will change from the project oriented to the results-oriented. The project website will include public technical reports, preprints and reprints (*links to electronic journals*), public documents about the project activities, links to other established connections and relevant projects for joint activities and collaborations.

All papers from the project will be made freely accessible on the project's website. Where there are restrictions from the publisher; such as an embargo period, pre-published versions of the articles will be put up instead. With regards to the project's deliverables, the vast

majority of them are public (PU), and will be made freely accessible through the project's website during the project duration and for another 3 years after the end of the project.

Best practices in **Search Engine Optimization (SEO)**, such as those presented in the Google's Search Engine Optimization Starter Guide and in the Google's Webmaster Guidelines will be taken into account to attract visitors. Reciprocal links with websites of relevant projects will be established in order to interest the intended audience.

3.3.3.2 Academic Journals

The project partners will disseminate results through publications in major international journals in the field of the research activities of the project. Academic and practitioner journals where the results can be disseminated through scientific (*peer reviewed*) publications will be selected according to their relevance with the individual project results. These journals will target main areas of the project (*e.g. ICT-enabled government, mobile government, collective intelligence, social sensing, social innovation, decision-support ICT systems, crowd sourcing, computational sociology, semantic web, Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management, participatory democracy, social informatics etc.*).

The consortium will ensure open, **free-of-charge access** to the end –user to peer - reviewed scientific publications relating to the project results and to digital research data generated during the project (*the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications and associated metadata*) via a repository for scientific publications (*e.g. subject-based/thematic repository*).

This will provide readers with access to **peer-reviewed scientific publications** and **research data free of charge** as early as possible in the dissemination process, and enable the use and re-use of scientific research results. An initial list of targeted scientific journals that are relevant for our project is presented in the **Appendix IV**. This list will be updated every month during the project duration by Gov2u and will be available to all partners on the project document repository (*Alfresco*).

3.3.3.3 Non-scientific publications

Non-scientific publications like EU magazines covering science, technology, business (*e.g. the magazines Research*eu focus, Research*eu results, Horizon-The EU Research & Innovation Magazine, Futuris Magazine etc.*) will be also a channel where articles related to the project and its results can be published.

Non-scientific articles related to the project and its findings will be also submitted for publishing on websites that target Research and Innovation, Policing, Research dissemination (*e.g. the European Commission's Research & Innovation website, the Market Place of the European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities, the Social Innovation Europe website etc.*) as well as on websites of NGOs and professional associations, online informal groups from the pilot sites/countries that are interested by the topic of the project.

3.3.3.4 Public Events

The participation of the project partners to public events (*conferences, seminars, workshops*) is essential to disseminate project's activities and outputs to a targeted audience specialized or interested in personalised citizen-centric public service.

During these events promotional materials of the project (*brochures, flyers etc.*) will be distributed to the attendants if possible. In addition presentations of FLOOD-serv results will be displayed in PPT format. For achieving the widest visibility of the project, each consortium

partner will introduce its results and perspectives or contribute to the project dissemination through at least 2 events or publications over the FLOOD-serv lifecycle.

WP6 leader has created the initial list of targeted events (*see Appendix V*) where all partners will be responsible for updating it. It will contain major European events as well as national ones and will be supplied with more public events every 3 months. In case of finding any new possibilities interesting from dissemination point of view, partners shall report them as soon as possible to Gov2u in order to coordinate the further actions.

The project partners will also present the results in exhibition and technology transfer seminars and will participate in the concentration activities and meetings related to the ICT-enabled open government projects. All available information about national, European and International Conferences will be evaluated and opportunities for publishing papers or oral presentations will be identified.

Overall, the activities that will accompany the consortium's participation in public events are:

- WP6 leader will be asked to **print dissemination material** (*the number of copies shall be defined by the partner that will attend the event*) and/or update the available ones with up-to-dated project's results.
- **Feedback from audience** (*participants of the event*) may be collected at the events where the project will be presented. This feedback could be useful for providing valuable information on project's general reception as well as some "commercial" feedback for the future (*see also section 5.2 Quantitative Measurements*).
- **Informational Booths**
- A **small report** (*1-2 paragraphs*) will be provided to WP6 leader for sharing the outcomes of the events with the stakeholders via the project's website, social media and so on.

3.3.3.5 Relevant Websites

Cross-links between our project website and other relevant websites will be also established e.g. websites of European networks and communities such as Citizen Focus Action Cluster on EIP Smart Cities and Communities communication and information hub, network of organizations of Digital Social Innovation, RRI Community of Practice, the Spanish technological water platform (*PTEA*), etc. The [DRMKC web-platform](#) facilitates information and knowledge sharing, while enhancing the connection between science, operational activities and policy. Information about FLOOD-serv events, results and lessons learned can be disseminated on this web-platform.

3.3.3.6 FLOOD-serv social media accounts

The project's social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn were created during M1 and on Google+ during M2. Additionally, in M6 (*January 2017*) the Community of Interest LinkedIn group will be created (*based on the FLOOD-serv LinkedIn account*). In this group information that further promote the FLOOD-serv results in a more targeted manner concerning the pilot sites will be shared. Under the framework of promoting the project's results these accounts will be constantly updated with posts about:

- FLOOD-serv **publications**;
- FLOOD-serv **public deliverables**;
- FLOOD-serv **press releases**;
- FLOOD-serv **e-newsletter issues**;
- **Events** such workshops, presentations and so on **organized by the consortium**;

- Results from **other EU funded projects** that respectively support FLOOD-serv by sharing information about it;
- FLOOD-serv **videos** for presenting the platform.
- Share links from FLOOD-serv profiles on **digital publishing platforms** (*i.e. Issuu, SlideShare and Scribd*) where project's results will be available.

The FLOOD-serv social media accounts will be managed and updated by Gov2u, WP6 leader. However, all partners are responsible to provide content, information from their dissemination activities and news and/or developments of their work that would possibly interest the target audiences. For this reason, one post per week (*at least*) on each account will be made. The increase of posts' visibility will be assisted by the usage of hashtags.

A **hashtag**⁴ is a type of metadata tag used on social networks such as Twitter and other microblogging services, allowing users to apply dynamic, user-generated tagging that makes it possible for others to easily find messages with a specific theme or content; it allows easy, informal markup of folk taxonomy without need of any formal taxonomy or markup language. Users create and use hashtags by placing the number sign or pound sign # (*also known as the hash character*) in front of a string of alphanumeric characters, usually a word or unspaced phrase, in or at the end of a message. The hashtag may contain letters, digits, and underscores. Searching for that hashtag will yield each message that has been tagged with it. A hashtag archive is consequently collected into a single stream under the same hashtag.

In our case, hashtags can be effective in promoting a project's event and/or results such as project's public deliverables, publications and so on. Incorporating hashtags in FLOOD-serv social media content can attract large audience. The selected hashtags for the promotion of the project are the following:

- #FloodEmergency
- #MobileTechnologies
- #OpenGovernment
- #SocialMedia
- #AwarenessService
- #Transparency
- #CitizenEmpowerment
- #EU_Project
- #H2020
- Locations of pilot sites
- Other words relevant with project's publications
- Official hashtags of public events where consortium partners presented the project

Taking into consideration that the FLOOD-serv is in its initial phase (*M4*) and no major results are yet available, this activity will be dissemination oriented in a more mature phase of the project.

3.3.3.7 Mailing Lists

Separate mailing lists for each type of target audience will be created and used to disseminate information, news, press releases and project products. The mailing lists will be updated constantly.

⁴ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hashtag>

3.3.3.8 Other Channels

If possible, channels established by the ICT-enabled open government projects and other similar projects (*e.g. EU co-funded projects that enhance disaster prevention and preparedness and are funded under the Civil Protection Mechanism*) will be used for the dissemination activities of our project, including common workshops and joined-up activities. Joint activities could include but are not limited to cross-referencing other projects' websites and distributing promotional material to other projects' events, publications in the project newsletters. The project will be also promoted on LinkedIn among groups of practitioners and professionals on disaster risk management, flood risk management, e-government etc. (*e.g. LinkedIn group on disaster risk reduction and resilience - LinkedIn group on e-government/e-citizen*).

4 Calendar of Dissemination Activities

This chapter is consisted by a representation of the scheduled FLOOD-serv dissemination activities on a calendar and an overview of the WP6 actions performed until M4 that will assist the consortium to realize the presented plan. This calendar ensures that all types of audiences can have access to the presented information of this document and will not be discouraged of reading it.

4.1 The Calendar

Following up the analysis made about the FLOOD-serv Dissemination Plan in **chapter 3**, the current section gives a detailed description around the planned actions (*What & How?*) accompanied by the expected date of completion (*When?*), partners' involvement (*Who?*), audience type (*To whom?*) and where (*Location*). All the above constitute the "Calendar".

The events that the consortium will attend throughout the 36 months of project's lifecycle are partially presented. All information around the events is not available yet as this deliverable is submitted in M4 (*November 2016*). However, a list with targeted events that will be suggested to WP6 partners to participate are available in **Appendix V**.

<i>What & How</i>	<i>When</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>To Whom</i>	<i>Where</i>
e-Newsletter Issue No.1	Month 4 (<i>November 2016</i>)	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All target audience	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Non-scientific article (<i>writing and submission</i>) to present the project to Non-scientific publications like EU magazines covering science, technology, business (<i>e.g. the magazines Research*eu focus, Research*eu results, Horizon-The EU Research & Innovation Magazine, Futuris Magazine etc.</i>)	Month 5 (<i>December 2016</i>)	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	General Public	Pilot countries and all other EU countries

LinkedIn group creation for members of the Community of Interest	Month 6 <i>(January 2017)</i>	Gov2u will create the group, partners from the pilot sites will assist in inviting members.	Members of the Community of Interest	Main focus in pilot countries without excluding all other EU countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.2	Month 8 <i>(March 2017)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All target audience	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Press release to announce the findings published in D2.2 and D2.3	Month 11 <i>(June 2017)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	General Public	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.3	Month 12 <i>(July 2017)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All target audience	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Workshop (including an information booth) organized within the 2017 Major Cities of Europe conference	The date of the annual conference of the Major Cities of Europe that will take place during Y1 of the project.	CELLENT leads the activity, Gov2u will support by providing dissemination material	Leading experts of Innovation in cities, local government organisations, academic institutions and not-for-profit organisations	EU countries
Press release to announce the progress of the project in defining the FLOOD-serv functional and technical specifications for FLOOD-serv system components	Month 14 <i>(September 2017)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	General Public	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.4	Month 16	Gov2u leads the activity,	All audiences	Pilot countries and all

	<i>(November 2017)</i>	contribution by all partners		other EU countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.5	Month 20 <i>(March 2018)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Press releases in each pilot country to announce the implementation of the national pilots	Month 22 <i>(May 2018)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.6	Month 24 <i>(July 2018)</i>	Gov2u Contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Press release to demonstrate the FLOOD-serv Integrated System	Month 24 <i>(July 2018)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	General Public	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Workshop (<i>including an information booth</i>) organized within the 2018 Major Cities of Europe conference	The date of the annual conference of the Major Cities of Europe that will take place during Y2 of the project	CELLENT leads the activity, Gov2u will support by providing dissemination material	Leading experts of Innovation in cities, local government organisations, academic institutions and not-for-profit organisations	EU countries
Presentation (<i>incl. an information booth</i>) of FLOOD-serv technology at the Smart Cities Expo World Congress 2018	The date of the annual Smart Cities Expo World Congress that will take place in Y2 of the project	CELLENT leads the activity, Gov2u will support by providing dissemination material	Entrepreneurs, research centers, universities and other public or non-governmental organizations or	EU countries and beyond

			consortiums (<i>public-private</i>) with innovative Smart City ideas, studies, visions and solutions	
Video to present D4.6 Integrated system	Month 26 (September 2018)	Exdwarf leads the activity with contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.7	Month 28 (November 2018)	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
e-Newsletter Issue No.8	Month 32 (March 2019)	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Research brief submission (by e-mail)	Month 34 (May 2019)	IP Tulcea with contribution by all partners	Other similar projects, scientific and academic communities	EU countries and beyond
Final project brochure to present the final results (creation and printing)	Month 35 (June 2019)	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All audiences	EU countries and beyond
Research brief submission (by e-mail)	Month 35 (June 2019)	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	Other similar projects, scientific and academic communities	EU countries and beyond
e-Newsletter Issue No.9	Month 36	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all	All audiences	Pilot countries and all

	<i>(July 2019)</i>	partners		other EU countries
Press release to announce the end of the project and its results	Month 36 <i>(July 2019)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	General Public	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Research brief submission <i>(by e-mail)</i>	Month 36 <i>(July 2019)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	Other similar projects, scientific and academic communities	EU countries and beyond
e-Newsletter Issue No.10	Month 36 <i>(July 2019)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	Pilot countries and all other EU countries	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Non-scientific article <i>(writing and submission)</i> to present the project results to EU magazines covering science, technology, business, websites that target Research and Innovation, Policing, Research dissemination as well as on websites of NGOs and professional associations, online informal groups from the pilot sites/countries	Month 36 <i>(July 2019)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	All audiences	Pilot countries and all other EU countries
Final publishable summary report (EN) <i>(creation and printing)</i>	Month 36 <i>(July 2019)</i>	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all partners	50 participants to the Final conference	EU countries
	Month 36	Gov2u leads the activity, contribution by all	At least 50 participants <i>(EU institutions and agencies,</i>	EU countries

Final conference of the project in Brussels, Belgium	(July 2019)	partners in inviting stakeholders	<i>members of European networks, coalitions and NGOs)</i>	
Workshop (<i>including an information booth</i>) organized within the 2019 Major Cities of Europe conference	The date of the annual conference of the Major Cities of Europe that will take place during Y3 of the project.	CELLENT leads the activity, Gov2u will support by providing dissemination material	Leading experts of Innovation in cities, local government organisations, academic institutions and not-for-profit organisations	EU countries
Presentation (<i>incl. an information booth</i>) of FLOOD-serv technology at the Smart Cities Expo World Congress 2019	The date of the annual Smart Cities Expo World Congress that will take place in Y3 of the project	CELLENT leads the activity, Gov2u will support by providing dissemination material	Entrepreneurs, research centers, universities and other public or non-governmental organizations or consortiums (<i>public-private</i>) with innovative Smart City ideas, studies, visions and solutions	EU countries and beyond
Publication of Scientific articles in Conjunction of Conference proceedings or articles in Scientific Journals	To be identified during the project implementation	Dissemination and Exploitation Board, Contribution by all partners	Scientific and academic communities	EU countries and beyond
Oral presentations and posters at Conferences	To be identified during the project implementation	Dissemination and Exploitation Board, contribution by all partners	Scientific and academic communities, industry and public sector representatives	EU countries and beyond

Present the technology in exhibitions, technology transfer seminars, brokerage events	To be identified during the project implementation	Dissemination and Exploitation Board, contribution by all partners	IT Industry, consulting firms, public authorities	EU countries and beyond
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Table 6 : Calendar of FLOOD-serv main dissemination Activities

4.2 WP6 actions performed until M4

Within the frame of preparing the ground for the dissemination actions that will be made in a more mature phase of the project WP6 has already created the tools that will assist in realizing the planned activities. During the first 4 months of the project WP6 has created:

- A “**corporate design**” for the project took place in the first month of the project with a view to apply it in different media that will be used to disseminate the project’s results and products. In this regards, the project’s visual identity was created (*through a Logo and Document templates for reports, for PPT presentations, for newsletter, for press releases, promotional materials*).
- A **project website** was launched in September 2016 (M2) to provide project-specific information to the public and the community of interest, to disseminate press releases, reports and project’s results. The URL is: www.floodserv-project.eu
- **Social media accounts** (*Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn*) during August 2016 (M1) and Google+ during September 2016 (M2). All social media accounts were activated by the launch of the project website.
- Accounts in **digital publishing platforms** i.e. Slideshare, Scribd, Issuu, were created for making the projects results (*public deliverables, papers etc.*) available to wider audience.
- **e-Newsletter** creation and submission of the first issue

Screenshots of the aforementioned materials and tools are available in the **Appendix VII**.

5 Performance Measurement of Dissemination Activities

The implementation of the actions described in this deliverable will be monitored by the WP6 leader and their performance will be constantly discussed and evaluated among the project partners. The successfulness of this dissemination plan will be based in **quantitative** and **qualitative** measurements. This chapter is mainly focused on the quantitative measurements without however neglecting the qualitative ones.

5.1 Quantitative Measurements

The consortium's long run experience in EU funded projects as well as the WP6 obligations that arise from the DoW form the standards for evaluating the performance of the dissemination actions. These standards i.e. **Key Performance Indicators (KPI's)** assist the FLOOD-serv in distinguishing whether this plan is effective or corrective actions are needed to be made. In the deliverables D6.3 "First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan" and D6.6 "Final Communication and Dissemination Report" respective reports for the examined periods will be included.

5.1.1 Website's indicators measurement

The measurement of these indicators will be made via the **Google Analytics** tool.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Page views per month	≥ 400
Visits per month	≥ 80
Returning visits	≥ 30%
Average duration of individual visits	≥ 1 min

Table 7 : Website's indicators measurement

5.1.2 Facebook's indicators measurement

The measurement of these indicators will be made via **Facebook Insights**.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Total Page Likes (<i>in Y1</i>)	≥100
Total Page Likes growth per year	≥65%
Reach per month (<i>on average</i>)	≥300
Post Engagement per month (<i>on average</i>)	≥90
Posts per month	≥4

Table 8 : Facebook's indicators measurement

5.1.3 Twitter's indicators measurement

The measurement of these indicators will be made via the **Twitter Analytics** tool.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Followers (<i>in Y1</i>)	≥100
Followers growth per year	≥65%
Tweet impressions per month (<i>on average</i>)	≥300
Profile visits per month (<i>on average</i>)	≥30
Tweets per month	≥4

Table 9 : Twitter's indicators measurement

5.1.4 LinkedIn's indicators measurement

There is no tool available for measuring the performance of a LinkedIn profile. However, the number of connections is available by LinkedIn.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Connections (<i>in Y1</i>)	≥100
Connections growth per year	≥65%
Posts per month	≥4

Table 10 : LinkedIn indicators measurement

5.1.5 Google+ indicators measurement

There is no tool available for measuring the performance of a Google+ profile. Nevertheless, the number of followers is available by Google.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Followers (<i>in Y1</i>)	≥10
Followers growth per year	≥50%
Posts per month	≥4

Table 11 : Google+indicators measurement

5.1.6 Newsletter's indicators measurement

Information around the newsletter subscribers will be derived from the backend of the project's website.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Subscribers to e- Newsletter (in Y1)	≥60
Subscribers growth per year	≥65%

Table 12 : Newsletter's indicators measurement

Besides the number of subscribers to the e-newsletter, the performance of the project's e-newsletters will be monitored based on the following metrics:

- **Unsubscribe rate:** the percentage of subscribers who chose to opt out of receiving newsletter content in the future;
- **Read and clicked rates for the email version of the newsletter:** data refers to opened email messages only, and show how many of them were just read but not clicked and how many of them were clicked to visit the project site.
- **Bounce rate for the email version of the newsletter:** the percentage of total emails sent that could not be delivered to the recipient's inbox.
- **Delivery rate for the email version of the newsletter:** the percentage of messages which ended up in subscribers' inboxes.
- **Spam complaint rate for the email version of the newsletter:** how many of emails were marked as spam by the recipient.

5.1.7 Digital Publishing Platforms indicators measurement

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Number of documents related to the project published per year on Scribd, Slideshare and Issuu	≥5
Number of views (on average) per document on each File sharing site	≥15

Table 13 : Digital Publishing Platforms indicators measurement

5.1.8 YouTube's indicators measurement

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Number of videos published per year	3
Number of views (on average) per video	≥100

Table 14 : You tube's indicators measurement

5.1.9 Media indicators measurement

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Number of articles about the project published in printed and	≥20

online media throughout project's lifetime	
Number of interviews/News about the project broadcasted at radio and/or TV throughout project's lifetime	≥3

Table 15 : Media indicators measurement

5.1.10 Other indicators measurement

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>Indicator of Success</i>
Scientific articles published in journals	To be defined
Non-scientific articles published in magazines and specialized websites	4
Number of third party events where the project and its results will be presented	5
Links/ Articles/ References in FLOOD-serv partners' institutional websites, newsletters, social media accounts throughout project lifetime	≥20
News items, announcement of events and FLOOD-serv information in specialized blogs and websites throughout project lifetime	≥20
References in third parties websites and publications about the project throughout its lifetime	≥15
Cross-links with other 3rd parties / projects websites throughout project's lifetime	≥5
Number of relevant stakeholders for the Community of interest identified and contacted by email by Month 12	≥100
Percentage of contacted stakeholders who accept to be members of the Community of interest	≥25%
The rate to which the members of Community of Interest abandon this community till the end of the project	Maximum 10% of the members
Number of communication materials (<i>flyers, brochures</i>) printed and distributed	To be defined
Number of formal and informal collaborations with other projects	≥5

Table 16 : Other indicators measurement

Other quantitative indicators:

- Number of references in scientific publications
- Number of project events organized

- Number of participants in project events
- Countries of project website's visitors
- Number of people asking for feedback or more information about the project via the contact form/e-mail address from the project website

5.2 Qualitative Measurements

The qualitative measurements do not consist statistical indicators but qualitative variables that can help the FLOOD-serv consortium to understand the satisfaction of target audience from the project's dissemination actions. The above will be achieved by feedback questionnaires addressed to participants of project's workshops and events, visitors of the website and so on.

They can be distributed during project events or sent out by mailing list to attendees aiming to receive from them useful information about:

- whether the event fulfilled their expectations;
- the FLOOD-serv technology developed;
- their willingness to use it;
- their willingness to pay for use and / or how much.

6 Conclusions

This document draws the plan for the actions that will be followed for disseminating the project's outcomes with main scope to achieve significant awareness of the initiative, an understanding of its benefits and active interaction with necessary stakeholders.

It is addressed to a wide audience consisted by:

- FLOOD-serv project partners;
- European Commission;
- Target groups (*End-users, decision makers/replication actors, stakeholders, policy makers*);
- Representatives of organizations involved into similar projects;
- Anyone interested.

For ensuring that anyone interested in the FLOOD-serv project can have access to the presented information of this document and will not be discouraged of reading it, a representation of the scheduled dissemination activities on a calendar is included.

Its successfulness is based on **quantitative** and **qualitative** measurements that will distinguish if corrective actions will be needed or not. In any case, the deliverable "*D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan*" that will be submitted in M19 will give a clear view about the level of effectiveness of this plan.

APPENDIX I – WP6 contact points

<i>WP6 Partner</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Contact Person</i>
SIVECO S.A. ROMANIA	Romania	Lavinia Panait
GOVERNMENT TO YOU	Belgium	Pantelis Kanellopoulos
CELLENT AG	Austria	Susanne Sonntagbauer
ANSWARETECH SL	Spain	Beatriz Rodriguez
INTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE - DEZVOLTARE DELTA DUNARI	Romania	Alexandru Banescu
AYUNTAMIENTO DE BILBAO	Spain	Izaskun Llona
A.N.O. SISTEMAS DE INFORMATICA E SERVICOS LDA	Portugal	Teresa Pacheco
EXDWARF CONSULTING SRO	Slovakia	Tomáš Koreň
INSTITUTIA PREFECTULUI JUDETUL TULCEA	Romania	Maria Naparu
BRATISLAVSKY SAMOSPRAVNY KRAJ (BSK)	Slovakia	Katarina Vargova
MUNICIPIO DE VILA NOVA DE FAMALICAO (CMVNF)	Portugal	Manuel Pinheiro
COMUNE DI GENOVA	Italy	Maurizio Michellini

APPENDIX II – Dissemination Rules and Guidelines

The rules and guidelines that all partners should be aware when implement and report the dissemination and communication activities are:

Coordination

- Gov2u is responsible for coordinating the dissemination process.
- SIVECO is responsible of keeping partners informed about the project progress.
- Each partner is responsible for coordinating the dissemination process within its organization among the project staff and other staff that may benefit from the project results and the knowledge resulted from the project.

Teleconferences

- Teleconferences will be set up by SIVECO and a doodle poll will define the exact date and time of the teleconference.
- Minutes of the teleconferences and project face-to-face meetings will be created by SIVECO and distributed to all partners in maximum 3 days after each meeting.

Media

- All partners are responsible for the project coverage in media at national level such as printed articles, interviews in newspapers, audiovisual announcements, etc.
- A list of press focal points of all partners has been established. The press focal points will translate the press releases and distribute them in their national media, while they will be also responsible for the media coverage monitoring following the press releases submission.
- All partners are responsible for media enquiries, setting up interviews and writing articles related to the project.

Production of communication materials and promotional items

- All articles, press releases and newsletters shall be previously internally reviewed by the Consortium before to be made available to the public.

Publications in journals and conference proceedings

- Open access publications
- An initial list of targeted journals is presented in the **Appendix IV**
- Call for papers of relevant academic conferences will be monitored by Gov2u. The Consortium will have to decide if there will be submitted papers and/or will be made oral and poster presentations at academic conferences that will be selected
- Partners should collaborate to produce join research papers related to the project.

Presentation at events

- All partners are responsible of updating the list of events where the project and its results can be presented. Gov2u has provide in **Appendix V** an initial list with major European events and all partners shall complete it with their national events. It is expected that the list to be updated every 3 months. In case of finding any new

possibilities interesting from dissemination point of view, partners shall report them as soon as possible to Gov2u

- All presentations at events shall be made on the PPT template created for this purpose.
- Partners that will attend an event where the project will be presented can contact Gov2u to ask for dissemination material and if printed material is available.
- Feedback from audience may be collected at the events where the project will be presented. This feedback could be useful for providing valuable information on project's general reception as well as some "commercial" feedback for the future. Collecting such feedback shall be based on short, previously prepared questionnaire or interviewing carefully adjusted to the particular event and its target audience. The questionnaire/interviewing guide shall be prepared by Gov2u with help of other partners, mainly ones actively involved in the selected event.
- Informational Booths
- Each partner that participates in and/or attends an event on behalf of FLOOD-serv and/or presents the project has to contact Gov2u and give a small report (*1-2 paragraphs*) about the outcome of the event and possible feedback received by other attendees/visitors – in maximum 5 days after the event
- After the project has been presented at an event, a brief information will be published on the project site and presentations and any accompanying publications will be uploaded on the project website in maximum 3 days after the event.

Updating the project website content

- The public deliverables will be published on the project informational website after they have been submitted to the European Commission with watermark "Pending for Approval". When the deliverables will be approved within 3 days the status of the document will change in "Approved".

Social media management

- At least once per week Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ will be updated.
- Gov2u is responsible for updating the social media accounts of the project. However all partners are responsible to provide news and/or developments of the projects that may interest the stakeholder and the wide audience.
- Distribution of materials on Slideshare, Scribd, Issuu

Liaison with other projects

- An initial list of projects to liaison with is provided in **Appendix VI**. The list will be updated and presented in the Deliverable D6.3
- Gov2u will lead this activity but all partners can contribute in approaching similar projects with FLOOD-serv.

Visual identity

The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (*including the media and the public*) in a strategic and effective manner. Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the Agency (*see Article 52 of Grand Agreement*).

Unless the *Agency* requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (*including in electronic form, via social media, etc.*) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

1. display the EU emblem and
2. include the following text:

For communication activities: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693599”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: “This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693599”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the *Agency*. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means. Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the *Agency* is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Reporting procedure

All partners will have to report their communication and dissemination activities every 3 months as it was decided unanimously by all them during the first general assembly of the project. They will have to use the reporting template that is provided in **Appendix III**.

Events Guidelines

The Events guidelines document includes a comprehensive set of guidelines to advise FLOOD-serv partners on the correct process to follow with regard to the organization as well as the participation and attendance at events where the project is presented during its timeline.

All partners are responsible for updating dissemination information. The most frequently updated information will be the Events list. Gov2u provided the partners with a detailed Events list including major events focused on the project’s thematic area. Partners have to update these tables regularly including relevant events at national level and deliver them to Gov2u in order to include them in the updated version of the Events list. The update will be provided every 3 months or just after some new events will be identified. In case of finding any new possibilities interesting from dissemination point of view, partners shall report it to Gov2u.

Before and after the project has been presented at events, some brief information will be published on the project informational website and presentations and any accompanying publications will be downloadable from the website. All events shall be accompanied by leaflets and brochures distributed to event’s participants and/or posters put in relevant places to attract the wider audience. All these promotional materials are available and downloadable from the website and the consortium’s document sharing platform.

Media Guidelines

Press releases are a major communication tool serving the wide dissemination, visibility raising and promotion of the project. Useful guidelines on the process for successful press release dissemination and monitoring of the media coverage have been provided by Gov2u to all partners to ensure that communication policy is respected throughout the consortium. The first step required is the nomination of a press focal point per partner. The press focal points team is responsible for the preparation of a media list at national level, the translation and distribution of the press releases to all media outlets and the monitoring of the media coverage.

Moreover, Gov2u and the partners' press focal points have to monitor on a monthly basis the media coverage achieved such as collect press clippings, links of the announcements of the press release, etc. and send them to Gov2u in order to publish them on the FLOOD-serv project website and include this information in dissemination reports. Press focal points have to monitor mostly search engines but also EU news resources, industry publications, etc. for the project website and relevant to FLOOD-serv clippings. Gov2u will regularly send an email to all press focal points to remind them to send any press clippings. This internal document is available in the document sharing platform.

Guidelines on Communication at national level

The dissemination and communication strategy is important at national level; therefore WP6 provides some guidelines about how partners should address people in their national or local settings and connect with citizens.

WP6 partners must appoint a person from their organization as responsible in dealing with dissemination/communication. Once this is done and the person given this authority to speak and coordinate with the media has been identified, WP6 partners can follow the guidelines given below to facilitate their dealing with them:

- It is important to understand clearly the dissemination and communication objectives and to keep in mind the communication & dissemination goals, what needs to be achieved and how it can be achieved
- The right tailored message must be used: identify your target audience and ensure that the message can be easily understood by your target audience. The message should into account the information needs of the various groups that you want to reach
- The message receiver is the final destination of the message. The receiver will interpret the message according to their own logic, perspective and knowledge. A well-expressed message can be more easily understood by the receiver and thus it can be disseminated in a proper way that will bring the expected results
- Communication is not a one-way process and therefore we consider that when we send a message to someone, this person will react to the message received
- It is imperative to listen: take peoples' views and concerns into account
- For media relationships to work, mutual respect should be established with journalists and the relationship should be based on this trust. You must keep them informed when you have genuine news to share
- It is important to be proactive: Draw the journalists' attention to key events and developments of particular interest

- If for whatever reason you are not able to answer a journalists' question, try to refer them to someone else in the project who can assist
- It is really important for dissemination and communication activities to estimate the impact of your actions and your strategy. Therefore please collect press clippings, links, videos etc. and send them to the dissemination and communication team so they can be uploaded on the Media section of the project website
- Each one of the project partners markets the project and contributes to its wider promotion at national level by all possible means. It is important to take the initiative and send available promotional material to journalists of your media list.
- The participation in various relevant events highly increases the project's visibility and triggers user engagement and involvement. Therefore, you can look for relative events in your country and try to participate; alternatively you can also check the Events list on the document sharing platform the consortium is using, under Dissemination. Once you confirm your participation to an event, you shall inform the dissemination and communication team so you can disseminate the event and your presentation there.
- Write articles
- It is important to use the template created for the presentation of the project, thus keeping the project identity
- If a presentation is given to a non-scientific or non-specialized audience, please keep the presentation clear, simple and to the point
- It is also equally important to use plain spoken language in you presentations and documents so that most people can understand without requiring further explanation
- You can send your translated press releases or other material to the dissemination and communication team to upload them on the website in the Media section. It is clear that the visibility of the project is highly dependent on the way we promote it and the tools that we use.

APPENDIX III – Reporting Template

Reporting template of Dissemination Activities

All partners who have contribution in WP6 will complete the following tables every 3 months in order to report their dissemination activities to WP6 leader. Gov2u will keep a record of these reports for each partner for monitoring their activities as well as guiding and supporting these actions. Below the tables are provided.

Reporting template

Please fill in the following tables with the dissemination activities that you have performed during the reporting period.

If you have undertaken more activities that do not match in the following sections, please write them at the end of the document.

A. Direct contact with target audiences

(Face-to-face meetings with target audiences)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name and type of the contact</i>	<i>Date of the meeting</i>	<i>Venue/Location of the meeting</i>	<i>Activity description (short description of the outcome of the meeting, what we gained from it)</i>

B. Communication with target audiences

(Communication with target audiences about the project via email, social media, phone, contact form of the website, etc.)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name and type of the contact</i>	<i>Date of communication</i>	<i>Reason of communication</i>	<i>Activity description (short description of the outcome of the communication, what we gained from it)</i>

C. Organization of events/press conferences/webcasts/webinars

(Events that partners organized about the FLOOD-serv)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event (city, country)</i>	<i>Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)</i>

D. Participation in third party events

(Partner's participation conferences, workshops, seminars, meetings, etc.)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event (city, country)</i>	<i>Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)</i>

E. Press Coverage of FLOOD-serv Project

(Press release, article, interview, website link, reference on webpage, reference in news items, etc.)

I. External

(Items only from 3rd party sources e.g. newspapers, radio/TV coverage, informational websites etc.)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Type of press item (press release, interview,</i>	<i>Title of the press item</i>	<i>Media where it was published</i>	<i>URL (if available)</i>

	etc.)			

II. Internal

(Items only from partners' communication channels e.g. partners' website, partners' social media etc.)

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Type of press item (press release, interview, etc.)</i>	<i>Title of the press item</i>	<i>Media where it was published</i>	<i>URL (if available)</i>

F. Scientific Publications

<i>Title of publication (in case of joint publication with other partner please mention- {joint})</i>	<i>Date of publication</i>	<i>Name of Author(s)</i>	<i>Journal, Publishing house (please provide URL if available)</i>	<i>Status (accepted/submitted/ presented to the conference proceedings and scientific journals)</i>

G. Collaboration with other projects

D6.2 Dissemination Plan

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the project you collaborated with</i>	<i>Contact person or organization</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description of the collaboration activity</i>

APPENDIX IV – Targeted scientific journals

The consortium will disseminate results through publications in major international journals in the field of the research activities of the project. The initial list with the targeted scientific journals where the results can be disseminated is provided in this appendix. It will be updated throughout the project's lifecycle and accordingly with the latest findings.

<i>Scientific Journals</i>	<i>Type of audience</i>
<u>Advances in Management Information Systems</u>	Researchers, practitioners and executives in the field of information systems.
<u>Communications of the Association for Information Systems</u>	Members of the IS community.
<u>Electronic Government, an International Journal (EG)</u>	Professionals, academics, researchers, managers, policy makers, and non-profit organisations.
<u>Electronic Journal of e-Government (EJEG)</u>	Researchers, individuals and organisations working in the field of e-Government/e-Governance, e-Democracy, e-Participation
<u>e-Service Journal</u>	Targeted towards those engaged in the academic and practical aspects of e-Business and e-Government.
<u>European Journal of Information Systems</u>	Information systems professionals in industry, commerce, government and academic departments of management, business and computing.
<u>IADIS International Journal on Computer Science and Information Systems</u>	Information Society community
<u>Information Systems Journal</u>	IS community
<u>Information, Communication & Society</u>	Scholars & Practitioners in Social Sciences, Gender & Cultural studies, Communication & Media studies, and Information & Computer sciences.
<u>International Journal of Human-Computer Studies</u>	Researchers in computing, artificial intelligence, psychology, linguistics, communication, design, engineering, and social organization
<u>International Journal of Electronic Governance</u>	Researchers, academics, professionals, managers, policy makers and non-profit organisations with an interest in the design and

	development of electronic governance.
<u>International Journal of Electronic Govt. Research</u>	Academicians, Practitioners, and Professionals
<u>International Journal of Information Management</u>	Senior managers in a variety of business and industrial organizations; information managers; public sector managers and administrators; management consultants; information scientists and system analysts; teachers and trainers in management; public administration and related fields; researchers in business; information management and information science.
<u>International Journal of Sociotechnology and Knowledge Development</u>	Practitioners, academics, researchers, and students
<u>International Journal of Technology, Knowledge and Society</u>	Academics in the fields of informatics, computer science, history and philosophy of science, sociology of knowledge, sociology of technology, education, management and the humanities; research students; technology developers and trainers and industry consultants.
<u>Journal of Community Informatics</u>	Academics, CI practitioners, and National & Multi-lateral policy makers
<u>Journal of Computer Mediated Communication</u>	Scholars in communication, business, education, political science, sociology, media studies, information science, and other disciplines
<u>New Media & Society</u>	Includes contributions from communication, media and cultural studies, as well as sociology, geography, anthropology, economics and the political and information sciences
<u>The Information Society (TIS) Journal</u>	Policy, decision-makers & scientists in government, industry & education; managers concerned with the effects of the information revolution on individuals, organizations and society; academic researchers.

APPENDIX V – Targeted Events

The list of the targeted events is provided in this appendix. It will be updated during the project's lifecycle according with its latest findings.

<i>Title of the event</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Countries addressed</i>
<u>ISCRAM 2017, 14th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response And Management</u>	21-24 May, 2017	Albi, Occitanie Pyrénées-Méditerranée, France	EU countries and beyond
<u>ICFR 2017 : 19th International Conference on Flood Resilience</u>	26-27 February 2017	Barcelona, Spain	EU countries and beyond
<u>10th IADIS International Conference on Information Systems 2017</u>	10 – 12 April 2017	Budapest, Hungary	EU countries and beyond
The International Conference on Information Society (i-Society) 2017	Not defined yet	-	-
<u>IEEE ICC'17: Bridging People, Communities, and Cultures</u>	21-25 May 2017	Paris, France	EU countries and beyond
<u>UMAP 2017</u>	9-12th July, 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	EU countries and beyond
<u>WSDM2017 (Web Search and Data Mining)</u>	6-10 February 2017	Cambridge UK	
<u>Major City Events</u>	To be defined	Zagreb, Croatia	EU countries and beyond
Open Innovation 2.0 Conference 2017	To be defined	To be defined	To be defined

Table 17 : List of targeted events

APPENDIX VI – Related EU funded projects

The following table presents the projects that are related with FLOOD-serv and it is planned to establish collaborations with them. This list will be updated throughout project's duration.

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Description</i>
Mobile Age www.mobile-age.eu	Mobile Age project focuses on open government data, mobile technology, and the provision of public services in relation to Europe's elderly population.
DIGIWHIST www.digiwhist.eu	DIGIWHIST's goal is simultaneously to increase trust in governments and improve the efficiency of public spending across Europe.
CLARITY www.clarity-csa.eu	The CLARITY project will support European Member States in their pursuit for greater trust, transparency and efficiency within their open eGovernment initiatives and highlight best practice within this field.
Smarticipate www.smarticipate.eu	Through smarticipate citizens will be given access to data about their city, enabling them to better support the decision-making process.
RECAP www.recap-h2020.eu	The overall objective is to develop and pilot test a platform for the delivery of public services that will enable the improved implementation of the CAP, targeting public Paying Agencies, agricultural consultants and farmers.
YDS (Your Data Stories) www.yourdatastories.eu	The project will cater the publishers of open governmental data on how to foster meaningful and useful government data publication, by bridging the gap between the "supply side" and the "demand side". In this context, YourDataStories aims to meet the citizen and business needs by putting open data into good and innovative uses, promoting data use, re-use and re-purposing, ultimately enhancing transparency and corruption fighting.
WeLive www.welive.eu	WeLive aims to bridge the gap between innovation and adoption of open government services and to catalyse public services by empowering citizens and businesses to directly participate in the design, creation, selection and delivery of some of the public services in the form of mobile apps.
ROUTE-TO-PA www.routetopa.eu	ROUTE-TO-PA is a multidisciplinary innovation project that, by combining expertise and research in the fields of e-government, computer science, learning science and economy, is aiming at improving the impact, towards citizens and within society, of ICT-based technology platforms for transparency.

<p>OpenBudgets.eu www.openbudgets.eu</p>	<p>OpenBudgets is an EU funded project, aiming at supporting journalists, civil society organisations, NGOs, citizens and public administrations, by providing an overview of public spending, as well as tools and appropriate data and stories to advocate and fight for fiscal transparency.</p>
<p>Euth www.euth.net</p>	<p>EUth (Tools and Tips for Digital and Mobile Youth Participation in and across Europe), stands for a digital European youth participation platform, accessible by administrations and youth organizations to set up participative processes.</p>
<p>OpenGovIntelligence www.opengovintelligence.eu</p>	<p>The OpenGovIntelligence project aims at stimulating sustainable economic growth in Europe through innovation in society and enterprises. OpenGovIntelligence suggests a holistic approach for the modernisation of Public Administration (PA) by exploiting Linked Open Statistical Data (LOSD) technologies. This includes new business processes, policies, and tools that would enable the active participation of the society and enterprises in data sharing and in the co-production of innovative data-driven public services.</p>
<p>SIMPATICO www.simpatico-project.eu</p>	<p>SIMPATICO's goal is to improve the experience of citizens and companies in their daily interactions with the public administration by providing a personalized delivery of e-services based on advanced cognitive system technologies.</p>
<p>STEP www.step4youth.eu</p>	<p>TEP aims to develop and pilot test a cloud eParticipation SaaS platform, enhanced with web / social media mining, gamification, machine translation, and visualisation features, which will promote the societal and political participation of young people in the decision-making process on environmental issues.</p>
<p>WeGovNow www.wegovnow.eu</p>	<p>WeGovNow will tap into emerging technologies for effectively supporting co-production by civic society stakeholders and collective proposition development, whereby citizens are partners, as opposed to customers, in the delivery of public services.</p>

Table 18 : List of related EU funded projects

APPENDIX VII – WP6 performed actions until M4

A. FLOOD-serv Logo

Figure 4 : Project logo

B. FLOOD-serv Website

Figure 5 : Project's website

C. Facebook Page

Figure 6 : Facebook Page

D. Google+ Profile

Figure 7 : Google+ Profile

E. Twitter Account

Figure 8 : Twitter Account

F. LinkedIn Account

Figure 9 : LinkedIn Account

G. Scribd Account

Figure 10 : Scribd Account

H. Slideshare Account

Figure 11 : Slideshare Account

I. Issuu Account

Figure 12 : Issuu Account